

Effect of Stacking Sequence in Cross-Ply Graphite/Epoxy Laminates on Acoustic Emission Results

J. Awerbuch¹⁾, J. Block²⁾, R. Prinz²⁾

- 1) Department of Mechanical Engineering and Mechanics, Drexel University, Philadelphia, PA 19104, U.S.A.
- 2) Institute for Structural Mechanics, Deutsche Forschungs-und Versuchsanstalt fur Luft-und, Raumfahrt e.V. (DFVLR), Vraunschweig D-3300, W. Germany

ABSTRACT

This study concentrates on monitoring damage initiation and progression through acoustic emission in cross-ply graphite/epoxy T300/914C laminates. Data recorded include accumulative events and counts, count-rate and number of counts per event as a function of load, line location and amplitude distribution histograms of events, and the Cumulative Events Amplitude Distributions (CEAD) at different load levels, all for emissions occurring within a pre-set area of interest along the specimen. The results demonstrate a potential for using acoustic emission to locate existing damage, detect and track damage initiation and progression, identify potential fracture sites, and possibly distinguish between the major failure mechanisms of different laminates, all of which will ultimately aid in forecasting the strength and life of the individual specimens during proof-testing. Emphasis is placed on developing the proper test methodology for characterizing a new composite material system through acoustic emission.

Two graphite/epoxy cross-ply laminates were tested: $[0/90]_2$ and $[90_2/0_2]_8$. All specimens were tested at stroke control at a rate of 0.5mm/min. Two types of loading functions were employed: 1. monotonically increasing load up to failure; 2. loading/unloading cycles at predetermined incremental loads up to failure. Acoustic emission (AE) was monitored using Dunegan/Endevco 3000 series AE instrumentation. The most pertinent operating parameters are: Transducer type S9204, threshold level of 40 dB, fixed gain of 40 dB pre-amplifier, voltage gain of 40 dB, dead time = 10 msec, spatial filtering (window) set at 10-90. Transducers were placed at both ends of the specimen with an interim distance of approximately 200 mm.

Additional non-destructive examinations were performed to correlate the results obtained through monitoring acoustic emission with those obtained by X-ray radiography. An extensometer of 40 mm gage length and strain gages were also used on some of the specimens.

A good degree of reproducibility has been established for both laminates in the load at which AE initiates (damage initiation), in the plots obtained for events and counts versus load, and in the number of counts per events as load increases. Also, location and amplitude distributions of events and

CEAD were highly reproducible.

However, a distinct difference exists between all of the AE parameters recorded for $[0/90]_{2s}$ and $[90_2/0_2]_s$ laminates:

In the $[90_2/0_2]_s$ laminate AE initiates at approximately 25% of the ultimate load while in the $[0/90]_{2s}$, AE initiates at approximately 50% of ultimate load. This is primarily attributed to the matrix cracking of the 90° plies (first ply failure - FPF), which in the $[90_2/0_2]_s$ laminate are not fully constrained by the 0° plies and thus fail at a much lower load level. This phenomenon has been affirmed by both visual observations and X-ray radiography.

Location distribution histograms of events, correlated with X-ray radiographs, indicated that initiation of FPF could be located for the $[90_2/0_2]_s$ laminate. For the $[0/90]_{2s}$ laminate, however, emission occurred throughout the specimen length and such a detection was not possible. It should be emphasized that in the $[90_2/0_2]_s$ laminate, FPF is followed by edge delamination causing the unsupported 90° -deg. plies to snap prematurely. Amplitude distribution histograms of events are also distinctly different for each laminate. The results obtained for the $[90_2/0_2]_s$ laminate suggest a potential for distinguishing among the three major failure mechanisms, namely matrix cracking, delamination and fiber fracture.

During unloading/reloading cycles it has been determined that emission begins prior to the previous maximum load level. The AE initiation load depends upon the load history of the system and upon the subject material. This test procedure indicates a potential or an acceptance-rejection criterion, e.g. providing a qualitative measure of existing damage and forecasting failure load.

The effects of the type of transducers used and the emissions from specimen gripping have also been determined. Results indicate a significant effect on all AE parameters recorded.

Accumulative events as a function of load for cross-ply graphite/epoxy laminates. Emission initiation load depends on laminate stacking sequence.

AE initiation load ratio during unloading/reloading cycles as a function of applied stress for cross-ply graphite/epoxy laminates. Slope depends on laminate stacking sequence.

Amplitude distribution histograms for graphite/epoxy [0/90]_{2s} laminate at various load levels.

Amplitude distribution histograms for graphite/epoxy [90₂/0₂]_s laminate at various load levels.

Accumulative events as a function of load obtained at two pre-set windows for graphite/epoxy [0/90]_{2S} laminate. Significant effect of window on AE results.

Accumulative events as a function of load obtained from two different transducers. Choice of transducer affects AE results.

